

A RESEARCH ON DETERMINING THE LEVEL OF TOURISTS' SATISFACTION REGARDING KAZAKH CUISINE

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Abstract

The main purpose of this research is to determine the satisfaction levels of foreign tourists visiting Kazakhstan regarding local cuisine. In addition, the determination of tourists' visit motives, behavioral intentions. The universe of the study consists of foreign tourists who visit Almaty city and experience unique Kazakh food and drinks. Data were collected through face-to-face interviews using the questionnaire technique. The evaluations of foreign tourists arising from their eating and drinking experiences in Kazakhstan are grouped into seven dimensions which are: local foods, personnel quality, facility quality, culinary culture, visit effect, menu, and price dimensions. It was determined that there were significant differences according to gender, frequency of visit, the purpose of visit, nationality, and age variables towards the local cuisine satisfaction of tourists. It can be said that the level of satisfaction of the tourists with the local foods and beverages they experience in Kazakhstan is high. There is a positive relationship between tourist satisfaction dimensions (local food, facility quality, visit effect, and price satisfaction) and frequency of tourists visiting Kazakhstan. It has been concluded that tourists visiting for leisure purposes give more importance to the quality of personnel, the quality of the facility, and the price.

Keywords: Kazakh cuisine; Tourist satisfaction; Service quality; Gastronomy tourism.

UMA PESQUISA SOBRE COMO DETERMINAR O NÍVEL DE SATISFAÇÃO DOS TURISTAS EM RELAÇÃO À CULINÁRIA CAZAQUE

Resumo

O principal objetivo desta pesquisa é determinar os níveis de satisfação dos turistas estrangeiros que visitam o Cazaquistão em relação à culinária local. Além disso, a determinação dos motivos da visita dos turistas, intenções comportamentais. O universo do estudo consiste em turistas estrangeiros que visitam a cidade de Almaty e experimentam comidas e bebidas cazaques únicas. Os dados foram coletados por meio de entrevistas face a face utilizando a técnica de questionário. Foram analisadas as avaliações de turistas estrangeiros decorrentes de suas experiências de comer e beber no Cazaquistão, agrupadas em sete dimensões: alimentos locais, qualidade do pessoal, qualidade das instalações, cultura culinária, efeito da visita, cardápio e de preço. Determinou-se que havia diferenças significativas de acordo com as variáveis sexo, frequência da visita, objetivo da visita, nacionalidade e idade quanto à satisfação dos turistas com a gastronomia local. Pode-se dizer que o nível de satisfação dos turistas com os alimentos e bebidas locais que experimentam no Cazaquistão é elevado. Existe uma relação positiva entre as dimensões da satisfação do turista (comida local, qualidade das instalações, efeito da visita e satisfação do preço) e a frequência dos turistas que visitam o Cazaquistão. Concluiu-se que os turistas que visitam por motivos de lazer dão mais importância à qualidade do pessoal, à qualidade das instalações e ao preço.

Palavras-chave: Cozinha Cazaque; Satisfação do turista; Qualidade do serviço; Turismo gastronômico.

UNA INVESTIGACIÓN SOBRE LA DETERMINACIÓN DEL NIVEL DE SATISFACCIÓN DE LOS TURISTAS CON RESPECTO A LA COCINA KAZAJA

Resumen

El objetivo principal de esta investigación es determinar los niveles de satisfacción de los turistas extranjeros que visitan Kazajstán con respecto a la cocina de Kazajstán. Además, la determinación de los motivos de visita de los turistas, intenciones de comportamiento. El universo del estudio consiste en turistas extranjeros que visitan la ciudad de Almaty, Kazajstán, y experimentan comidas y bebidas exclusivas de la cocina kazaja. Los datos fueron recolectados a través de entrevistas cara a cara utilizando la técnica del cuestionario. Se analizaron e interpretaron las relaciones de las valoraciones de los turistas extranjeros derivadas de sus experiencias de comer y beber en Kazajstán en siete dimensiones: alimentos locales, calidad del personal, calidad de las instalaciones, cultura culinaria, efecto de la visita, menú y dimensiones del precio. Se determinó que existían diferencias significativas según las variables género, frecuencia de visita, motivo de la visita, nacionalidad y edad en lo que respecta a la satisfacción de los turistas con relación a la gastronomía. Se puede decir que el nivel de satisfacción de los turistas con los alimentos y bebidas locales que experimentan en Kazajstán es alto. Existe una relación positiva entre las dimensiones de satisfacción del turista (comida local, calidad de las instalaciones, efecto de la visita y satisfacción con el precio) y la frecuencia de los turistas que visitan Kazajstán. Se ha concluido que los turistas que visitan por motivos de ocio dan más importancia a la calidad del personal, la calidad de las instalaciones y el precio.

Palabras clave: Cocina Kazaja; Satisfacción del turista; Calidad del servicio; Turismo gastronómico.

1 INTRODUCTION

Gastronomy tourism is a great idea for those who want to visit other countries to have new experiences and get to know the culinary culture or enjoy different cuisines (Sandybayev, 2019). Tourists seek new and authentic

experiences and new tourism trends make gastronomy an important attraction (Ramazan, 2019). Gastronomy is an important element of culture and a way of accessing cultural and historical heritage for tourists. High-quality and popular food and beverages contribute to the satisfaction level of tourists. Thus, innovative and creative practices are

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developing in traditional cuisines to increase the quality of the tourist experience (Garibaldi, Pozzi & Viani, 2016).

Culinary culture may be one of the factors taken into consideration by tourists during destination selection. Therefore, tourists who are not purely for gastronomy purposes also exhibit behaviors that can be evaluated within the scope of gastronomy tourism during tourism activities. According to the World Tourism Organization report, tourists allocate one-third of their total expenses to food and beverages during their travels.

Occasionally the desire to enjoy authentic cuisine is the major motivation for travel. For instance, gastronomic tours are available in Italy, France, and Scandinavian countries for local cuisine and also in Scotland as whiskey tours. It can be said that there is significant potential to develop gastronomy tourism in Kazakhstan.

Kazakhstan has rich history and multi-ethnicity, special food & beverage and processing techniques and preserved authentic dishes, etc. Such elements form the basis of the traditions kept alive in today's culinary culture. Kazakh cuisine is unique because of the factors such as the manner of food arrangement, the rituals it contains, etiquette, tangible and intangible dimensions of food culture, etc.

In addition, it can be said that the natural and geographical conditions have a great impact on the development of Kazakh cuisine. It is stated that legends, rituals, ceremonies, and traditions covering food customs are directly related to the nomadic lifestyle of Kazakhs in their past periods (WTO, 2012).

Therefore, it is noteworthy that although there is a potential for the development of gastronomic tourism in Kazakhstan, there are limited academic studies on it. Chernyavskaya and Kauymbayev (2017) aimed to examine the concepts of national Kazakh culinary promotion tools, natural products, original food and beverage recipes, compliance with halal food standards and the possibility of applying them to the fast-food format.

This study is based on a literature review and survey conducted to investigate the promotion of national cuisine and halal food in Kazakhstan. Research was conducted on data based on interviews with managers and employees of a prominent dining restaurant of various formats in Taraz, located in the Southern region of Kazakhstan. In the study of Sandybayev (2019), the main concepts of innovative gastronomic tourism as an opportunity for the development of Kazakhstan regions and their active participation in the formation of innovative tourism attractiveness were investigated by interviewing experts.

Tiberghien (2020) investigated the concept of authentic neo-nomadic culture as a regional brand for Kazakhstan's tourism development. In the research, the interview method for the tourists who participated in the Kızılaray and Tulip tour in Kazakhstan was used. Interviews were held with tourists who participated in the tours and experienced the national Kazakh food and beverage.

As it is understood from the study examples given above, it seems that there is no empirical and conceptual research that measures the satisfaction levels of foreign tourists visiting Kazakhstan and experiencing Kazakh food and beverages in national Kazakh restaurants. Therefore,

based on this research gap, it was decided to investigate the satisfaction levels of foreign tourists from Kazakh cuisine.

Because it is thought that the fact that tourists know and prefer Kazakh cuisine well and are satisfied with Kazakh cuisine will contribute to the development of gastronomy tourism in Kazakhstan and to increase the quality of service in national Kazakh food and beverage businesses. It is assumed that the satisfactory service quality provided will also positively affect the behavioral intentions of foreign tourists. In this context, it is aimed to determine to what extent foreign tourists visiting Kazakhstan who know Kazakh cuisine, their level of preference for Kazakh cuisine products and their satisfaction with food and beverage businesses.

In this context, the following questions were developed to determine the factors that affect the satisfaction levels of foreign tourists in Kazakh cuisine:

- How satisfied are foreign tourists visiting Kazakhstan from national restaurants where they experience Kazakh cuisine?
- To what extent does Kazakh cuisine affect tourists' revisit of Kazakhstan?
- How important is the Kazakh cuisine in the food and beverage consumption of foreign tourists during their visit to Kazakhstan?

It can be said that the study is important because the suggestions developed in the light of the results obtained can contribute to Kazakhstan tourism, food and beverage businesses, and researchers interested in the subject.

2 THEORETICAL REVIEW

2.1 Local Cuisine and Tourism

Eating and drinking activities are a physiological necessity of human beings. This necessity sometimes gains different dimensions beyond the main reason. In addition to its vital importance, food is also seen as an inseparable element of culture in the context of cuisine (Çalışkan et al. 2020).

Culinary culture is directly related to geography, climate, local food sources, traditions, history, and religion. For centuries, food abundance and culinary wealth have been used by people as indicators of status and authority (Chernyavskaya & Kauymbayev, 2017). Moreover, tourists can experience local culture by consuming local foods in the destination during their trips (Ünlüönen & Işın, 2018). The tourists' experience of culinary culture in the destinations they visit is examined within the scope of gastronomy tourism.

Local food and beverages, which have an important place in the context of gastronomy tourism, attract the attention of tourists acting within the scope of any type of tourism and impact their spending preferences. And spending preferences have great impact on the local people and the local economy, and generate source of income (Şengül & Türkay, 2016). In this context, local cuisine is defined as "all of the foods and beverages that are created as a result of combining products specific to the region with local customs, cooked in their own way by the local people, and designed with religious or national feelings." (Şengül & Türkay, 2016).

Local cuisine and tourism have a strong relationship and mutual interaction with each other (Jalis, Che, &

Markwell 2014). For this reason, local cuisines are known as one of the most basic elements used to enhance destination identity and preserve cultural diversity and authenticity (Aşık, 2018). In particular, local cuisines introduce the ultimate indicator of the intangible heritage in a specific destination, allowing tourists to gain authentic and cultural experiences through the consumption of local foods (Okumuş et al., 2007).

The magnitude of food and beverage consumption of tourists stimulates the marketing and promotion activities of tourism destinations (Kim & Eves, 2012). It is stated that the role of gastronomy products is abundant in terms of destination marketing and promotion of tourists (Zengin & Şeyhanlioğlu, 2019).

Alderighi et al. (2016) revealed that positive perceptions of local foods affect positively the revisit intention of tourists for the same destination. However, they also stated that local food is one of the main elements in the development of the destination by branding and strengthening the brand image.

On the other hand, Kim & Eves (2012) listed the motivations and factors that push tourists to local foods such as an exciting experience, escape from routine, health concerns, cultural experience, being togetherness, prestige and sensory appeal, and stated that these factors are determinants of the choice of local food and beverage. In addition, among the factors that push tourists to travel is the desire to try new foods and beverages (Karakuş, 2019).

Pestek & Cinjarevic (2014) examined the effects of local cuisine on tourist satisfaction also the dimensions of tourists' experience with local foods during their holidays. As a result of this research, they stated that the tourists' experience and levels of satisfaction concerning the local cuisine differ in four dimensions which are "food uniqueness and cultural heritage", "food quality and price", "nutrition and health benefits of the food" and "affective image of the food".

In another study, it was determined that local cuisines offer opportunities to provide a positive image in tourism destinations, create new business opportunities and help their development (Alonso & Liu, 2011). Positive food image shows tourists' beliefs, feelings and impressions about food and beverage, businesses and culinary culture in the destination (Ramazan, 2019).

Information about local cuisines attracts and encourages tourists to enjoy local and/or ethnic foods (Du Rand, Heath & Alberts, 2003). Moreover, sector representatives should pay attention to conveying correct information about the local cuisine experience to tourists to produce positive messages about the destination. Thus, tourists will be able to increase their satisfaction by experiencing the local cuisine. However, the importance of providing satisfactory services to tourists by developing new foods with exotic flavors and authentic ingredients that meet the expectations of tourists should not be overlooked (Ryu & Jang, 2006).

Sandybayev (2016) revealed that basic practices related to gastronomy tourism are an abundant opportunity for the development of various regions in Kazakhstan and the formation of tourist attractions. He also stated that gastronomy tourism can be used in the context of destination image and brand building strategy and that there is an important potential in this regard.

2.2 Tourist Satisfaction

Since customer satisfaction is one of the most valuable issues for the businesses, it is known that satisfied customers have a significant impact on the profits (Atikahambar et al., 2018). In other words, customer satisfaction is known as the output of goods and services that meet customer needs (Sabir et al., 2014).

However, in the tourism literature, satisfaction is referred to as a function of tourists' expectations before and after travel. In this direction, tourist satisfaction consists of two different dimensions: the first is related to the tourist's expectations before the trip; the second is the justification of the tourist-based on post-travel perceptions and real experiences (Aliman et al., 2016). Therefore, tourist satisfaction is known as one of the most abundant factors in associating the development and attractiveness of tourism enterprises (Rahman et al., 2018).

Thus, in the studies of Ryu & Jang (2006) and Ling et al. (2010) have shown that both domestic and international tourists revisit intention increases as their level of satisfaction increases, and a positive food experience affects satisfaction level. As a result of the research, which aims to examine the relationship between tourists' satisfaction with Malaysian local foods and their behavioral intentions, it is emphasized that it will strengthen the idea of revisiting tourists to get experience the authentic food culture or it will lead to positive images in the minds of consumers and increase their satisfaction (Ling et al., 2010).

Rahman et al. (2018) stated in the study that the relationship between tourist satisfaction and consumer behavior mediates purchase intention. In addition, tourist satisfaction and perception have a positive impact on the intention to buy local foods, as well as a significant relationship between tourist satisfaction and perceived quality.

Another study found that local food is an important factor both in the satisfaction of tourists that seek new experiences, and also already of already experienced tourists (Roozbeh et al., 2013). In another study, it is stated that tourists feel different by consuming unique foods of the destination and factors such as "Cultural Heritage" and "Food Ingredients" effect on tourist satisfaction. As a result, it has been demonstrated that it is abundant to know which aspects of the tourists' food experience during their vacation are more pleasurable (Babolian Hendijani, 2016).

2.3 Kazakh Cuisine

Kazakhstan is home to the historical and cultural heritage of various ethnic groups due to it is a multinational country with geographically significant size. As a part of the cultural heritage gastronomy-related items are important in terms of tourism.

Gastronomy tourism is a type of tourism for tourists who want to get to experience the local cuisine of a country. Gastronomy tourism, which is a developing type of tourism in the world, also has significant development potential in Kazakhstan. It is integrated with the history of Kazakh cuisine and the development and formation of Kazakh society as a whole (Sandybayev, 2019).

Kazakh cuisine can be considered relatively new in terms of development. Because the transition of Kazakhs from nomadism to settled life was largely completed only at the end of the nineteenth century. This transition radically changed Kazakh economy and started to shape the culinary culture (Pokhlebkin, 2004).

Local cuisine is an integral part of national culture. Culinary culture is important within the scope of the image-building project called "Kazakhstan: Great Steppe Country" and in the context of the need for national brand development. Nowadays, local cuisine has become an instrument of a country brand, and attracting the attention of tourists from all over the world and an indicator of prosperity and national identity (Chernyavskaya & Kauymbayev, 2017).

Foreign tourists visiting Kazakhstan can participate in the "Gourmet Tour" in the Almaty region or the "Gastronomy tour" Dastarkhan to gain information about the local cuisine of Kazakhs. During this tour, starting with the city tour of Almaty, the best restaurants and wineries of the city are visited. With this tour program, tourists can see the ethnography museum and Kegen district where they can taste the local Kazakh cuisine. Tourists can also participate in Kazakh folk dances and competitions organized for them in the Kegen district (WTO, 2012). Food and beverage businesses not only offer traditional and local cuisine products as well as introduce other elements of the country's culture (Chernyavskaya & Kauymbayev, 2017).

The most important element to note about the prominent features of Kazakh cuisine is that unlike the cuisines of other Central Asian countries are made of horse meat, it is the preparation of sujuk (a kind of sausage), jal (a kind of boiled and sliced meat), karta (a kind of thick sausage) and sur (dried meat) dishes with the dough by boiling them in hot water.

Another feature of Kazakh cuisine is the use of hors offal such as liver, tripe, heart, kidney, brain, tongue, head, and trotter (feet) of the slaughtered animal and consumed with pleasure (Mukhatova, 2014). In addition, besbarmak (meat with dough), Kazakh meat (meat soup), mipilav (rice with brains), Kazakh bastirma (shish kebab), manti (made with pumpkin and potatoes), tushpara (a large type of boiled or roasted ravioli), orama (vegetable or meat-filled pastry) and kespe (noodle and vegetable soup), pilafs, kebabs made from animal and game meat are the main foods in Kazakh cuisine (Tlemisov, 1995).

Regarding the drinks, milk of different animals is used in Kazakh cuisine. Particularly nutritious and healthy "kumys" is made from horse milk and a drink called "shubat" is made from camel milk. Various kinds of butter and cheeses are fermented from cow, goat, and sheep milk (Mukhatova, 2014). Tea has begun to become widespread at the beginning of the eighteenth century. In Kazakh cuisine, milk tea, black tea, green tea, currant tea, meat tea (a kind of broth that does not contain tea leaves) are consumed. Although many of these teas differ concerning seasonal characteristics, most consumed tea is the milk tea (Katran, 2002).

In Kazakh cuisine, soups are prepared from slaughter meat, game meat, and fish. Various handmade kespe (noodles) and sometimes cereals are added to soups to make them rich in vitamins and more flavorful. The names of

the meat soups change according to the added ingredients. For example, there are varieties such as kaynatpa soup with greens (meat-vegetable soup), rice soup with meat, soup with meat-noodles, soup with meat-pumpkin, tushpara soup (like ravioli), chicken soup with greens (Bikenov, 2010; Tlemisov, 1995).

Foods prepared from grain and flour products are among the daily foods in Kazakh cuisine. Grain foods such as koje (a meal made from koje-split/cracked wheat), botka (milk-grain dessert), bilamik (butter and milk-grain dessert) are usually prepared by boiling method (Alimbai, 2011). Various pieces of bread are produced by roasting the fermented dough in vegetable oil or steaming it. Types of steamed bread are listed in Kazakh names as taba nan, tandyr nan, tandyr samsa (meaty bread). And types of baked bread in oil are kulshe, shelpek, balish, tokash, boursak, jayma, kattama, and kuymak (Katran, 2002; Tlemisov, 1995).

In Kazakh cuisine frequently consumed fruits are apple, plum, buckthorn berry, currant, raspberry, and strawberry. Kazakhs are engaged in horticulture (agriculture) in the southern regions and they grow various fruits such as melons, watermelons, and grapes. Especially melon and watermelon are dried for eating, and dried grapes are used in various foods, such as pilafs (Alimbai, 2012).

The most outstanding feature of Kazakh cuisine is that genetically modified organisms and food preservatives are not used in food and beverage products. So, it is possible to prepare healthy and environmentally friendly products. In this context, it can be said that different dishes prepared from non-GMO and environmentally friendly products may attract the attention of potential tourists.

However, with the impact of globalization in the world economy in recent years, restaurants serving European cuisine, Asian cuisine, and fast-food products have become widespread in Kazakhstan. This situation makes it difficult for Kazakhstan, which has a unique history and rich cultural heritage, to preserve its culinary culture, which is foremost part of the national asset (Sandybayev, 2019).

Nowadays, traditional Kazakh cuisine, known as diverse and versatile, is enriched by the form of new and original recipes. The use of halal foods in Kazakh cuisine is another practice that has gained importance in recent years (Chernyavskaya & Kauymbayev, 2017).

It can be said that gastronomy tourism is decidedly a means of integration between the countries of the world and one of the types of cognitive tourism. In this context, it can also be stated that for Kazakhstan to develop gastronomy tourism, it is necessary to educate talented cooks and staff who can adapt to changes in the world and accelerate to development of Kazakh cuisine (WTO, 2012).

It is critical for the development of gastronomy tourism and national restaurants to measure the presentation of local Kazakh foods as a tourism product in Kazakhstan and to reveal the satisfaction levels of foreign tourists in this research. In this context, the study aims to develop a scale by (Local Foods, Personal Quality, Facility Quality, Culinary Culture, Visit Effect, Menu, Price) combining the emerging themes related to the satisfaction levels of foreign tourists with local Kazakh foods (Table 1).

Table 1: Definition of Concept.

Concept	Definition	Reference
Local Foods	Local foods, attracting tourists to understand the intangible heritage, culture and culinary culture of a destination and encouraging travel	Du Rand et al. (2003); Sims (2009); Björk & Kauppinen-Räsänen(2016)
Personnel Quality	The personnels of the establishment are the providers of satisfaction for the needs and wishes of the tourists, the effective promoters, and educators of the local cuisine	Raajpoot (2002); Alonso & Liu (2011)
Facility Quality	To add value to the differentiation of service quality and satisfaction of tourists by providing specific tangible and intangible products of food and beverage establishments	Raajpoot (2002); Nam & Lee (2011)
Culinary Culture	Cultural assets with local food and beverage items that provide unforgettable culinary experiences to tourists	Smith & Costello (2009); Du Rand & Heath (2006)
Visit Effect	For tourists to revisit the destination to experience food and drink and recommend it to others	Prayag et al. (2013); Ab Karim & Chi (2010); Rahman et al. (2018);
Menu	It shows the innovation level of the food and beverage establishments in the production of the dishes, the variety of the products used in the foods and the sales products to the customers.	Raajpoot (2002); Smith & Hall (2003); Ozdemir & Caliskan (2015)
Price	The price of food and beverages attracts or repels customers, and also acts as an indicator of quality.	Raajpoot (2002); Saad Andaleeb & Conway (2006)

Source: own elaboration from the literature.

3 METHODOLOGY

The main purpose of this research is to determine to what extent foreign tourists visiting Kazakhstan who know Kazakh cuisine, their level of preference for Kazakh cuisine products and their satisfaction with food and beverage establishments. In addition, the determination of tourists' visit motives, behavioral intentions (revisiting the destination and/or recommending to others), evaluations of quality of business and staff are among the research sub-objectives.

3.1 Research Population and Sample

The population of the research consists of foreign tourists who have experienced Kazakh cuisine in Kazakhstan. The sample group includes foreign tourists visiting the region of Almaty. Almaty region was distinguished for data collection because it is the largest city in Kazakhstan in terms of population, it represents all regions in terms of gastronomic culture, and the number of qualified tourism and food and beverage businesses is high.

In the study, non-probabilistic convenience sampling method was used to collect data. Data were collected from 379 foreign tourists through convenience sampling. The data were collected using the survey technique through face-to-face interviews. From the collected survey forms, 14 forms were removed that were incomplete, and a data set was created on 365 surveys.

3.2 Data Collecting

To develop the survey that used in data collection, previously applied and validated surveys were used. Various sources were used in the creation of the variables in the survey. For the dimension of destination local cuisine satisfaction two statements adapted from Oral and Çelik (2013), two statements adapted from Royo-Vela (2009), two statements adapted from Tayfun & Arslan (2013), one statement adapted from Boo et al. (2009), and three statements were taken from Şengül (2016) and this dimension consisted of 10 statements in total.

For the dimension of revisiting the destination and recommending it to others (behavioral intention), two

statements adapted from Boo et al. (2009), two statements adapted from Çetinsöz & Artüger (2013), one statement adapted from Pike et al. (2013) as well as two statements adapted from Yılmaz (2009), and this dimension consists of seven statements in total. Eleven statements to reveal the perspectives of Kazakhstan's food and beverage businesses and also eight statements to determine the perspectives of the personnel working in these businesses were adapted from the study of Arslan (2010).

The survey consists of a total of 36 statements and demographic characteristics (gender, age, nationality, income status, vacation duration, and the number of arrivals) in two sections.

1. *Local Foods:* In general, the taste, variety, presentation in restaurants and positive image of local foods are the factors affecting the satisfaction of tourists. Local foods attract attention among the important factors that affect the purchasing decision of tourists and supply their expectations (Çalışkan et al. 2020).

2. *Personnel Quality:* In food and beverage establishments, the personnel's being attentive, friendly, helpful, communicable, polite, having information about food and beverage and providing information has an effect on the satisfaction of tourists (Genç et al., 2020).

3. *Facility Quality:* The fact that interior and exterior designs of food and beverage establishments have a beautiful, clean, well maintained and pleasant atmosphere, and pays attention to hygiene, service quality, and satisfaction of visiting customers affect the satisfaction of tourists (Karamustafa & Ülker, 2020).

4. *Culinary Culture:* The fact that the culinary culture has its own motifs, interesting and original foods, reflects the regional culture, traditions and characteristics affects the satisfaction of the tourists (Pekersen, 2020).

5. *Visit Effect:* Because tourists are satisfied with local food and beverages, they prefer the destination, like to visit and want to revisit (Rahman et al., 2018).

6. *Menu:* In food and beverage establishments, offering different menu options that include food and beverage contents and various food drinks in a way that tourists can understand has an effect on tourist satisfaction (Eren, 2019).

7. *Price*: The fact that the prices of the food and beverages offered in the food and beverage establishments are cheap and affordable affect the satisfaction of the tourists (Sabir et al., 2014).

The survey was evaluated by experts and pre-tested. Within the scope of the pre-test, a survey was applied to approximately 30 people selected from the population and the necessary changes were made in line with the feedback, and the final version was decided. The statements in the survey were translated into two languages, Russian and English, and applied to foreign tourists. A five-point Likert scale (strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, strongly agree) was used to determine their level of participation.

Frequency analysis was performed on the data obtained to determine the demographic characteristics of the participants. The reliability analysis was performed to decide whether the scale would be reliable or not. Explanatory factor analysis was performed to obtain fewer factors by gathering the statements together. Correlation analysis was applied to determine whether factor dimensions have a relationship with each other or not. T-test analysis and one-way ANOVA were applied to determine whether there is a significant difference demographic variables and factor dimensions.

3.3 Limitations of the Research

This research is limited to foreign tourists visiting Almaty in terms of time and cost. No financial support was received for the application of the survey. During the implementation of the survey form, were difficulties in obtaining permission from accommodation and food and beverage businesses.

4 RESULTS ANALYSIS

4.1 Findings on Demographic Characteristics

Descriptive information about the demographic characteristics of the participants is presented in Table 2. 59.5% of the participants are women, and a significant part of them are between the ages of 26-35. Most of the participants are foreign tourists from countries such as Russia, USA, Germany. 80% of tourists stay for four days and more, and 77% of them visiting Kazakhstan for leisure tourism. In addition, 72% of these tourists have visited Kazakhstan for the first time, and 53% are in the middle-income group.

Table 2: Frequency Analysis of Participants' Demographic Information.

Gender	N	%
Male	148	40.5
Female	217	59.5
Age	N	%
25 and below	74	20.3
26-35	133	36.4
36-45	81	22.2
46-55	31	8.5
56 and above	46	12.6
Country	N	%
Russia	44	12.1
USA	35	9.6

Germany	31	8.5
Turkey	22	6.0
UK	21	5.8
China	19	5.2
South Korea	16	4.4
France	15	4.1
Poland	14	3.8
Switzerland	12	3.3
Other-Europe	67	18.4
Other-Asia	22	6.0
Other-World	20	5.5
Missing value	27	7.4
Vacation Duration	N	%
Between one-three days.	74	20.3
Four days and more	291	79.7
Aim Of Visit	N	%
Other	83	22.7
Leisure tourism	282	77.3
Frequency Of Visit	N	%
Once	262	71.8
Two or more	100	27.4
Missing value	3	0.8
Income	N	%
Low	37	10.1
Average	192	52.6
High	123	33.7
Missing value	13	3.6
Total	365	100,0

Source: own elaboration from the research data.

4.2 Validity and Reliability Analysis

Reliability is used to measure internal consistency in the survey. Cronbach Alpha was used to calculate the reliability coefficients of the surveys. This coefficient measures the consistency of the statements in the measurement tools with each other. In the study, to eliminate the validity problem of the measurement tools, the scales whose validity is accepted in the sources were used and validation studies for the Turkish language were taken into consideration. The "Food and Beverage Services Perception Scale" with a coefficient of 0.94 was accepted as highly reliable as a measurement tool (Bagozzi & Yi, 1998).

To interpret the adequacy of the sample in which the factor analysis was applied the KMO value was measured as 0.928 by using the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measurement. As the KMO values between 0.5 and 1.0 are considered acceptable. In addition, values below 0.5 indicate that factor analysis is not suitable for the database in question. However, the minimum KMO value generally considered satisfactory to research is 0.7 (Çoşkun et al., 2017). Therefore, it could be said that the research sample is sufficient in terms of the KMO value measured as 0.928.

Factor structure was created with Varimax Rotation Principal Components Analysis and were found seven factors with eigenvalue greater than one which explained 66.143% of the total variance in Table 3. And the result of the Bartlett test was significant ($p > 0.000$). Factors dimensions and their percentages in total variance explained are "Local Foods" (15%), "Staff Quality" (14%), "Facility Quality" (10%), "Culinary Culture" (8%), "Visit Effect" (7%), "Menu" (6%), and "Price" (6%).

Reliability analysis was performed to determine whether these dimensions obtained as a result of factor analysis had internal consistency. Since the reliability coefficient (Cronbach's Alpha) for each dimension is above 0.70 (Local Foods=0,77, Personnel Quality=0,78, Facility Quality=0,78, Culinary Culture=0,78, Visit Effect=0,83, Menu=0,80, and Price=0,83), it can be said that reliability is high in terms of dimensions.

4.3 Data Presentation

According to the factor analysis given in Table 3, "Food and Beverage Services Perception Scale" is classified in

seven different dimensions. These factor dimensions are clear as follows: Local Foods dimension refers to the food and beverage products that tourists' experience about Kazakh cuisine. Personnel Quality dimension refers the human resources in the establishments that receive food and beverage services. Facility Quality dimension includes the tangible and intangible characteristics of the food and beverage business. Culinary Culture dimension refers to Kazakh cuisine as a whole. Visit Effect dimension refers to the impact of Kazakh cuisine on behavioral intention to revisit or recommend to others. Menu dimension refers to the understandability of the business menus. And the Price dimension refers to the perceptions of affordability of food and beverage products.

Table 3: Factor Analysis Results.

Factor	Factor Loadings	Eigen value	Variance	Factor Means	Cronbach's Alpha
Factor 1: Local Foods		5.037	15.262	3.92	0.770
I was satisfied with the local Kazakh cuisine.	0.800				
Local Kazakh cuisine is very tasty.	0.794				
I am positive about local Kazakh cuisine.	0.723				
All my reviews about local Kazakh cuisine are extremely positive.	0.706				
I was satisfied with the local Kazakh cuisine presented in restaurants.	0.687				
I think that Kazakhstan is one of those countries where presented high-quality local cuisine.	0.615				
I was satisfied with the variety of local cuisine.	0.543				
I advise to taste local Kazakh cuisine to my family, friends and colleagues.	0.468				
Factor 2: Personnel Quality		4.519	13.693	3.90	0.784
Attentive	0.745				
Friendly.	0.735				
Helpful.	0.729				
Communicable.	0.699				
Polite	0.671				
Owns information about foods and beverages.	0.654				
Good enough to provide information about foods and beverages.	0.642				
Factor 3: Facility Quality		3.411	10.336	3.89	0.781
Pays attention to the quality of service.	0.713				
Pays attention to hygiene.	0.686				
Beautiful interior.	0.657				
Pays attention to customer satisfaction.	0.638				
Clean and well maintained.	0.598				
Pleasant atmosphere.	0.553				
Factor 4: Culinary Culture		2.711	8.214	3.94	0.780
Has its own Kazakh style.	0.640				
Local Kazakh cuisine shows culture and traditions.	0.625				
I was satisfied with the originality of the local cuisine.	0.595				
Introduces the features of Kazakh cuisine.	0.567				
Local Kazakh cuisine is interesting.	0.557				
Factor 5: Visit Effect		2.375	7.197	3.09	0.831
I come to Kazakhstan to taste the local cuisine.	0.803				
Kazakhstan is on the list of countries with tasty local cuisine.	0.728				
I want to return to Kazakhstan to taste the local cuisine again.	0.666				
Factor 6: Menu		1.942	5.885	3.66	0.802
Affordable and clearer menu.	0.737				
All-age menu.	0.658				
Factor 7: Price		1.833	5.555	4.22	0.830
Cheap.	0.803				
The prices of local Kazakh cuisine are acceptable for me.	0.761				

Notes: Varimax Rotation Principal Components Analysis; Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy: 0,928; Bartlett's Test of Sphericity: $p > 0,000$; Chi-Square: 5786,046; df: 528; Total Variance Explained: 66,143; Response Categories: 1- Strongly disagree; 2-Disagree; 3-Neutral; 4-Agree; 5- Strongly agree.

Source: own elaboration from the research data.

The arithmetic mean of all dimensions except for the visit effect has a numerical value that expresses the participation status. Visiting effect dimension indicates a neutral attitude with an arithmetic mean of 3.09.

Results are presented in Table 4 according to the multi-correlation analysis. There is a significant and positive relationship between all the dimensions except for "price" and "visit effect". In Table 3, the highest correlation ensued between the personnel quality and the facility quality. In this

context, it can be concluded that food and beverage businesses are satisfied with the service quality. It can be said that as the satisfaction of the tourists' increases, the intention to revisit to experience local dishes and culinary culture. However, the lowest correlations appear in the menu and price dimensions. It can be said that tourists don't find a variety of local foods and beverages on the menu and are not satisfied with the prices of local foods and beverages.

Table 4: Correlations.

Factor	Means	Std. D	Local Foods	Personnel Quality	Facility Quality	Culinary Culture	Visit Effect	Menu	Price
Local Foods	3.91	.70	-						
Personnel Quality	3.90	.71	.514**	-					
Facility Quality	3.88	.66	.520**	.690**	-				
Culinary Culture	3.93	.64	.680**	.476**	.525**	-			
Visit Effect	3.09	.97	.660**	.300**	.280**	.440**	-		
Menu	3.65	.84	.422**	.482**	.521**	.447**	.221**	-	
Price	4.21	.76	.238**	.332**	.375**	.373**	.029	.321**	-

Source: own elaboration from the research data.

4.3 Differences in Demographic Characteristics

A t-test is performed to determine whether the demographic characteristics of tourists differ significantly by factor dimensions, and the results are given in table 5, 6 and 7 below. According to the gender variable significant differences are determined in terms of local foods, personnel quality, facility quality, culinary culture, and visit effect. In Table 4, it is seen that the arithmetic average of the answers given by female tourists is higher than males. In this context, the arithmetic average of the answers given by female tourists to "local foods" variable is 4.06 while it is 3.81 for males.

Table 5: Gender Differences.

Factor	Gender	Mean	t	P
Local Foods	Female	4.0623	3.323	.001**
	Male	3.8169		
Personnel Quality	Female	3.9972	2.097	.037*
	Male	3.8389		
Facility Quality	Female	3.9694	1.990	.047*
	Male	3.8287		
Culinary Culture	Female	4.0655	3.244	.001**
	Male	3.8467		
Visit Effect	Female	3.2297	3.323	.027*
	Male	3.0000		

** Significant at p<0,01 level, * Significant at p<0,05 level.

Source: own elaboration from the research data.

The average of the answers given by female tourists to "personnel quality" dimension is 3.99 while it is 3.83 for males. According to "facility quality" dimension, the average of the answers given by female tourists is 3.96 while it is 3.82 for males. The average of the answers given by female tourists to "culinary culture" variable is 4.06 while it is 3.84 for males. Similarly, the average of female tourists response to "visit effect" dimension is 3.22, while it is 3.00 for male tourists. Therefore, it can be said that women have more positive perceptions than men in terms of five dimensions in Table 4.

As result of the analysis, it was revealed that the dimensions of "local foods", "facility quality", "visit effect" and

"price" differ according to the frequency of visits as presented in Table 5. More tourists like local foods who have visited twice or more than other tourists who have only come once. According to the current situation, the tourists who have visited Kazakhstan the second time got used to Kazakh local foods compared to tourists who have only come the first time.

Table 6: Differences in Frequency of Visits.

Factor	Frequency of Visits	Mean	t	P
Local Foods	Once	3.8724	-2.086	.038*
	Two and more	4.0437		
Facility Quality	Once	3.9288	2.035	.043*
	Two and more	3.7697		
Visit Effect	Once	3.0108	-2.712	.007**
	Two and more	3.3183		
Price	Once	4.2824	2.561	.011**
	Two and more	4.0550		

** Significant at p<0,01 level, * Significant at p<0,05 level.

Source: own elaboration from the research data.

Tourists who have come for the first time find the facilities more qualified than tourists who have visited two or more. This situation can be interpreted as first-time tourists do not have high expectations for the facilities in Kazakhstan. Since their expectations are not high, they can evaluate the facilities as qualified. Revisiting tourists may have high expectations due to their previous experience.

In terms of visit effect, tourists who visited two or more times are different from those who come the first time. It was determined that the effect of Kazakh cuisine was among the reasons for repeat visits of tourists who visited two or more times. Tourists who have visited the first time do not pay more attention to the price of local foods than tourists who come twice or more. This may cause first-time tourists find local foods cheaper than their own country. Tourists visit Kazakhstan with such aims as "leisure tourism" and "other" tourism types (business, entertainment, medical, and sports tourism). The t-test results are given in Table 6 for explaining the differences in the aim of visit.

Table 7: Differences Regarding the Aim of Visit.

Factor	Aim of Visit	Mean	t	P
Personnel Quality	Other	3.7329	-2.498	.013**
	Leisure tourism	3.9532		
Facility Quality	Other	3.6928	-3.039	.003**
	Leisure tourism	3.9426		
Price	Other	3.7329	-2.777	.006**
	Leisure tourism	3.9532		

** Significant at $p < 0,01$ level, * Significant at $p < 0,05$ level.

Source: own elaboration from the research data.

A significant difference is determined between the “personnel quality”, “facility quality”, and “price” variables according to aim of visit. It can be said that leisure tourists give more importance to personnel quality, facility quality, and price according to tourists who aims other types. And there is no significant difference in factor dimensions as a result of t-test according to the duration of the visit.

One-way Anova test was conducted to determine whether the nationalities of the participants differ in terms of factor dimensions and the results are shown in Table 8. According to the country variable, significant differences are determined in terms of all dimensions as “local foods”, “facility quality”, “culinary culture”, “visit effect”, “menu”, and “price”. In this context, according to the post-hoc test on “local foods”, the source of this difference is determined between Poland and Germany, France, Other European countries, Other Asian countries. It can be said that tourists from Poland which is a country with a relatively limited variety of food, find and like much local Kazakh foods than other countries.

Table 8: Local Foods Dimension Difference Analysis by Countries.

Factor	Countries	N	Mean	F	P
Local Foods	Russia	44	4.1356	2.566	.003**
	U.S.A.	35	4.0776		
	Germany	31	3.6329		
	Turkey	22	3.9102		
	UK	21	3.7918		
	China	19	3.9461		
	South Korea	16	3.7679		
	France	15	3.6381		
	Poland	14	4.5204		
	Switzerland	12	3.9028		
	Other-Europe	67	3.8127		
	Other-Asia	22	3.7002		
Other-World	20	4.0071			

** Significant at $p < 0,01$ level, * Significant at $p < 0,05$ level.

Source: own elaboration from the research data.

According to the post-hoc test for the “quality of the facility” factor, the source of this difference is between Turkey and the USA, China, Poland, other world countries (Table 9). It can be said that tourists from Turkey find the quality of the facility low since the facilities in Turkey are more developed and modern compared to Kazakhstan in terms of facility quality and architectural construction.

Table 9: Facility Quality Dimension Difference Analysis by Countries.

Factor	Countries	N	Mean	F	P
	Russia	44	3.9735		
	U.S.A.	35	4.0476		
	Germany	31	3.7753		
	Turkey	22	3.4621		

Facility Quality	UK	21	3.7921	3.042	.000**
	China	19	4.1316		
	South Korea	16	3.5729		
	France	15	4.0778		
	Poland	14	4.3381		
	Switzerland	12	3.9028		
	Other-Europe	67	3.7587		
	Other-Asia	22	3.8879		
Other-World	20	4.1967			

** Significant at $p < 0,01$ level, * Significant at $p < 0,05$ level.

Source: own elaboration from the research data.

According to the post-hoc test on “culinary culture”, the source of this difference is between Poland and South Korea, Other European, Other Asian countries (Table 10). It can be said that the fact that Poland and Kazakhstan are quite different in terms of culinary culture, food preferences, and production techniques. So Polish tourists interested in Kazakh cuisine more than others.

Table 10: Culinary Culture Dimension Difference Analysis by Countries.

Factor	Countries	N	Mean	F	P
Culinary Culture	Russia	44	4.0936	2.188	.012**
	U.S.A.	35	4.0614		
	Germany	31	3.8849		
	Turkey	22	3.8886		
	UK	21	3.9905		
	China	19	3.9237		
	South Korea	16	3.7000		
	France	15	3.7400		
	Poland	14	4.4893		
	Switzerland	12	3.7833		
	Other-Europe	67	3.8254		
	Other-Asia	22	3.7273		
Other-World	20	4.0850			

** Significant at $p < 0,01$ level, * Significant at $p < 0,05$ level.

Source: own elaboration from the research data.

The post-hoc test of the “visit effect” suggests that the source of this difference is between Russia and France, England, Other European, Other Asian countries (Table 11). It is noticed that Russian tourists are familiar with Kazakh culinary culture compared to tourists from other countries mentioned, and hence they have the thought of visiting again.

Table 11: Difference Analysis of Visit Effect Dimension by Countries.

Factor	Countries	N	Mean	F	P
Visit Effect	Russia	44	3.5530	3.786	.000**
	U.S.A.	35	3.3524		
	Germany	31	2.9677		
	Turkey	22	2.9394		
	UK	21	2.6349		
	China	19	3.4211		
	South Korea	16	3.0833		
	France	15	2.4000		
	Poland	14	3.6190		
	Switzerland	12	3.1389		
	Other-Europe	67	2.8209		
	Other-Asia	22	2.7273		
Other-World	20	3.2833			

** Significant at $p < 0,01$ level, * Significant at $p < 0,05$ level.

Source: own elaboration from the research data.

According to the post-hoc test for the “menu” factor, the source of this difference is between Turkey and South Korea, also Russia and Poland (Table 12). It can be said that the menu content of Kazakh cuisine is not liked compared to other countries. For example, due to the high diversity of local dishes in Turkish cuisine, Turks may find limited menu with respect to South Koreans in Kazakhstan. It may be same for Polish and Russian tourists.

Table 12: Analysis of Menu Dimension Differences by Countries.

Factor	Countries	N	Mean	F	P
Menu	Russia	44	3.9886	3.062	.000**
	U.S.A.	35	3.7429		
	Germany	31	3.6613		
	Turkey	22	3.1364		
	UK	21	3.4286		
	China	19	3.7105		
	South Korea	16	3.2188		
	France	15	3.5000		
	Poland	14	4.2500		
	Switzerland	12	3.7500		
	Other-Europe	66	3.6515		
	Other-Asia	22	3.3409		
Other-World	20	3.9250			

** Significant at $p < 0,01$ level, * Significant at $p < 0,05$ level.

Source: own elaboration from the research data.

According to the post-hoc test for the “price” factor, the source of this difference is between other European countries and Russia, South Korea (Table 13). It can be said that tourists from other European countries find local food cheaper compared to Russia and South Korea due to the high level of income and the high value of their foreign currency in Kazakhstan.

Table 13: Price Dimension Difference Analysis by Countries.

Factor	Countries	N	Mean	F	P
Price	Russia	44	3.9659	3.478	.000**
	U.S.A.	35	4.4286		
	Germany	31	4.4839		
	Turkey	22	3.9545		
	UK	21	4.3571		
	China	19	3.8684		
	South Korea	16	3.7500		
	France	15	4.4333		
	Poland	14	4.3929		
	Switzerland	12	4.4583		
	Other-Europe	67	4.4478		
	Other-Asia	22	3.9091		
Other-World	20	4.1250			

** Significant at $p < 0,01$ level, * Significant at $p < 0,05$ level.

Source: own elaboration from the research data.

To determine whether there is a difference in dimensions according to age groups of the participants in the study, the one-way Anova test is performed and the results are shown in Table 14.

In terms of price dimension, a significant difference is determined according to age groups. According to the post-hoc test, the source of this difference is determined between the ages of 36-45 and 25 and below, 26-35. The participants of the 36-45 age group perceive the prices more reasonable than other age groups.

Table 14: Price Dimension Difference Analysis by Age.

Factor	Age	N	Mean	F	P
Price	25 and below	74	4.3649	4.224	.002**
	26-35	133	4.3459		
	36-45	81	4.0247		
	46-55	31	3.9516		
	56 and above	46	4.1087		

** Significant at $p < 0,01$ level, * Significant at $p < 0,05$ level.

Source: own elaboration from the research data.

Therefore, it can be said that as age increases, price sensitivity for local foods decreases. As a result of the one-way Anova, according to the income levels of the tourists no significant difference is found in terms of factor dimensions.

In Table 15, significant differences according to demographic variables and factor dimensions are summarized as a whole. In the table, it is seen that there are significant differences between gender, frequency of visit, purpose of visit, country and age demographic variables and all factor dimensions.

Table 15: Summary of Findings.

Analysis	Result
Gender differences by factor dimensions.	There are significant differences by all factors except for menu and price.
Differences in frequency of visits factor dimensions.	There are significant differences local foods, facility quality, visit effect and price factors.
Differences regarding the aim of visit factor dimensions.	There are significant differences by personnel quality, facility quality and price factors.
Local foods dimension difference nalysis by countries.	There are significant differences by Poland and Germany, France, other European countries, other Asian countries.
Facility quality dimension difference analysis by countries.	There are significant differences by Turkey and the USA, China, Poland, other world countries.
Culinary culture dimension difference analysis by countries.	There are significant differences by Poland and South Korea, other European, other Asian countries.
Difference analysis of visit effect dimension by countries.	There are significant differences by Russia and France, England, other European, other Asian countries
Analysis of menu simension differences by countries.	There are significant differences by Turkey and South Korea, also Russia and Poland Countries.
Price dimension difference analysis by countries.	There are significant differences by other European countries and Russia, South Korea.
Price dimension difference analysis by age.	There are significant differences between the ages of 36-45 and 25 and below, 26-35.

Source: own elaboration from the research data.

4.4 Data Discussion

As a result of the explanatory factor analysis applied to the satisfaction level scale of foreign tourists, seven dimensions were determined. These factors (local foods, personnel quality, facility quality, culinary culture, visit effect, menu, and price) have emerged that affect tourist

satisfaction. Within the scope of these dimensions, significant relationships and differences according to demographic variables were intended to be determined.

According to the results of the research, it can be said that the level of satisfaction of the tourists with the local foods and beverages they experience in Kazakhstan is high. Local foods and beverages seem to be an important elements for Kazakhstan's tourism attractions.

Significant differences are found between gender, frequency of visit, the aim of visit, country, age, and local cuisine dimensions. First, it has been observed that women are more satisfied than men with the dimensions of local foods, personnel quality, facility quality, culinary culture, and visit effect. These results differ from the results of Şengül (2016) and Şengel et al. (2015). There is a positive relationship between tourist satisfaction dimensions (local food, facility quality, visit effect, and price satisfaction) and frequency of tourists visiting Kazakhstan.

The results obtained regarding the frequency of visits are similar to the results of the studies conducted by Roozbeh et al. (2013) and Işkın (2021). It has been concluded that tourists visiting for leisure purposes give more importance to the quality of personnel, the quality of the facility, and the price. This result is similar with researches conducted by Nam & Lee (2011), Bayram (2017) and Correia et al. (2008). The values and lifestyles of tourists also affect the atmosphere, aesthetics and local food and beverage expectations in food and beverage establishments (Genç et al. (2020). These researches indicate that tourists are an important factor in the formation of local cuisine satisfaction in a positive way.

One of the important results of the research is determining the countries that generate the gastronomy tourism market of Kazakhstan. In this context, it has been observed that tourists from Poland are more satisfied with local Kazakh dishes and culinary culture. However, it is concluded that Turkish tourists don't satisfy with the quality of the facility and the menu. The results regarding the facility quality and menu variables partially support by the researches of Oralbekov & Auganova, (2018) and Yerdavletova & Mukhambetov (2014).

These researches mainly state that there is a lack of management quality and lack of diversifying local Kazakh foods and beverages in national restaurants. It has been concluded that Russian tourists have a high intention for revisiting Kazakhstan in order to experience local cuisine. This result is similar to the results of some researches as Arslan (2010), Ling et al. (2010) and Alderighi et al. (2016).

It has been concluded that other European countries tourists find local Kazakh food cheaper and they are satisfied with the price of local foods and beverages. It can be said that this situation is due to the high level of income of the tourists came from other European countries and the high value of their currency in Kazakhstan.

Similar results show that tourists attach more importance to the price of food (Neild et al., 2000) and the price dimension is the most important determinant of tourist satisfaction (Pestek & Cinjarevic, 2014). The assessment of local cuisine satisfaction by country can be particularly important, as many aspects of tourists' experiences are country-specific (Correia et al., 2008).

Finally, tourists in the 36-45 age group visiting Kazakhstan perceive the price of local foods and beverages as reasonable. Therefore, it can be said that as age increases, price sensitivity for local foods decreases. This result differs from the research conducted by Vuksanovic et al. (2019). In this context, local dishes, personnel quality, facility quality, culinary culture, visit effect, price, and menu factors can be seen as the holistic experience of gastronomy tourism and these factors are important elements of tourist satisfaction as reported by Correia et al. (2008).

Foods and beverage establishments especially operate in areas frequently visited by tourists, should use tourism as an opportunity to provide and promote more varieties of high-quality food with different tastes, interesting serving styles and appealing presentations. Thus, satisfying local food experiences will encourage tourists to revisit the destination and recommend it to others (Babolian Hendijani, 2016).

5 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Nowadays, an increasingly competitive environment within the framework of globalization causes product diversification in destinations. The demand of tourists for alternative tourism products are another factor to be considered. The change in the demands of tourists and their demand for different tourism products intensify the competition between destinations.

In this context, the way to gain a competitive advantage for destinations and businesses is to introduce new and different touristic products suitable for the demands of tourists. It can be said that one of the factors is local food and beverages that will provide a competitive advantage to the destination and differentiate it from other destinations. The authenticity of the food and beverages produced at the destination can contribute to increase tourists' revisit and other behavioral intentions such as suggesting other people about the destination.

Local foods and beverages are important elements of a tourism destination. However, the number of studies showing the importance of this subject for tourism in Kazakhstan is limited. For this reason, this study is conducted to show the importance of local foods and beverages that attract tourists to Kazakhstan and ensure their satisfaction. In this context, the satisfaction levels of foreign tourists visiting Kazakhstan regarding Kazakh cuisine are analyzed.

The gap that this study tries to fill is to determine the importance of Kazakh cuisine in presenting the main element in Kazakhstan gastronomic tourism and in influencing the experience, satisfaction levels and behavioral intentions of the visitors. In the existing literature, mostly conceptual studies have been made on Kazakh cuisine and Kazakhstan gastronomic tourism and the effects of tourists on the experience in the context of ethno-tourism have been discussed.

Unlike previous studies, (i) survey technique was applied in this study and Kazakh cuisine was chosen as a gastronomic tourism product. (ii) It has been determined that the local Kazakh cuisine is an important factor in ensuring the satisfaction of tourists. (iii) It has been determined that the

service quality of food and beverage businesses is important in the process of gastronomic tourism marketing. (iv) The contribution of national food and beverage businesses to the improvement of service quality has been demonstrated. (v) Local Kazakh food and beverage marketing strategies for the gastronomic tourism markets of Kazakhstan are discussed.

The following suggestions have been developed in the light of research results to use the gastronomic tourism potential of Kazakhstan and to increase the number of tourists and income:

- New Kazakh restaurants should be opened that reflect Kazakh culture.
- Quality of the facility of current Kazakh restaurants should be improved.
- The quality of personnel and facility should be compatible with tourist expectations and preferences.
- A reasonable pricing policy should be applied in Kazakh restaurants.
- Well-designed experience process of Kazakh cuisine should be created for the satisfaction of first-time tourists
- Diversified Kazakh food and beverages should be offered to repeat visitors.
- Ideal Kazakh cuisine menu should be created for all tourists and for all meals. However, the size of the portions and the menu of different types of food (vegetarian) can also be revealed.
- Kazakh cuisine should be promoted and marketed differently to tourists from culturally close countries and to tourists from other countries.
- Training and financial support should be provided to local tourism enterprises to organize and internationally promote gastronomic tours that require high costs,
- Skilled cooks and personnel who can adapt to the changes in the world and give impetus to Kazakh cuisine should be trained,
- Food, beverage and accommodation businesses should be supported for marketing activities,
- Especially scientific researches on local cuisines should be supported,
- Within the scope of the destination, cooperation should be established between local food and beverage producers and tourism enterprises,
- Attractiveness of destinations in terms of gastronomy should be determined and promotion should be made in this direction,
- The awareness of the local people about the local cuisine culture and gastronomy tourism should be increased.

This research is limited to collect data from the tourists visiting Almaty. And obtained data are analyzed within the framework of this constraint. Similar researches can be conducted in other destinations in Kazakhstan to expand the research findings.

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Term	Definition	1 st Author	2 nd Author
Conceptualization	Ideas; formulation or evolution of overarching research goals and aims	X	X
Methodology	Development or design of methodology; creation of models	X	X
Software	Programming, software development; designing computer programs; implementation of the computer code and supporting algorithms; testing of existing code components	X	X
Validation	Verification, whether as a part of the activity or separate, of the overall replication/ reproducibility of results/experiments and other research outputs	X	X
Formal analysis	Application of statistical, mathematical, computational, or other formal techniques to analyze or synthesize study data	X	X
Investigation	Conducting a research and investigation process, specifically performing the experiments, or data/evidence collection	X	
Resources	Provision of study materials, reagents, materials, patients, laboratory samples, animals, instrumentation, computing resources, or other analysis tools	X	X
Data Curation	Management activities to annotate (produce metadata), scrub data and maintain research data (including software code, where it is necessary for interpreting the data itself) for initial use and later reuse	X	X
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